

THE STATUS OF USING SOFTWARE THAT DEVELOPS STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK ACTIVITIES

Turayeva G.T.

Independent researcher at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizamiy

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Abstract. *Using the capabilities of the Hemis platform, which is currently used to manage the education system in higher education, and the combination of the functions of the Telegram messenger, which is popular among students, and the software that we offer that develops students' independent work activities, methods for effectively organizing independent learning in and outside the classroom were demonstrated.*

Keywords: *hemis, telegram, independent work, software, innovative activity, information, education, design, graphics.*

INTRODUCTION

The Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 aims to develop the necessary competencies of future specialists, creativity, research, and logical thinking by continuously developing students' independent learning and independent work skills, by increasing the share of independent learning hours, developing students' independent learning, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, and entrepreneurial skills, introducing methodologies and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, directing the educational process to the formation of practical skills, and in this regard, by widely introducing advanced pedagogical technologies, curricula, and teaching and learning materials based on international educational standards into the educational process.

The organization of independent work of students is one of the most urgent problems of the modern stage of education. It is associated with the systematic acquisition of new knowledge, which is the basis for the formation of cognitive independence, which is necessary for the professional formation of the teacher's personality. Analysis of some studies shows that insufficient attention is paid to solving the problem of organizing students' independent work. Its complexity and multifactorial nature indicate that it is very difficult to solve this problem using traditional forms of education. Thus, the actualization of independent acquisition of new knowledge is associated with the existence of a contradiction in the modern education system, which, on the one hand, consists in the need to acquire knowledge quickly, and on the other hand, is associated with the limited possibilities of assimilation of knowledge by the subject of education and acquisition of new knowledge through traditional teaching methods [1,2].

As we know, independent work is an activity carried out in the process of self-development, acquisition of professional skills, creative independent work, accumulation of knowledge, formation of practical skills, and critical thinking during student's curricular and extracurricular activities.

Based on this, the implementation of complex approaches to this activity is carried out through the creation of software [3].

Figure 1. Software model for implementing independent student work activities

The rapidly progressing globalization process has not spared the education sector. Today, science and technology are developing so rapidly that some innovations and technologies are already outdated before they are even discovered. In such conditions, achieving effectiveness in education requires teachers to conduct regular research in their field and update their database on each topic.

Simulators are being used in almost every aspect of the educational process. Simulator programs are being used in the medical field to train future surgeons and nurses, and business simulator game programs are being used in the commercial sector. One of the main reasons for using simulators is that they allow you to conduct virtual laboratory work without real equipment and facilities. This not only saves a lot of money, but also eliminates the need for them altogether. The fact that simulators require almost no financial resources allows students to repeat certain research many times. Another advantage of using simulators is that they are safe. Some research poses a risk to human life, such as flying airplanes, studying nuclear physics, and studying chemical phenomena. Such studies not only require large financial costs, but also pose a risk to the lives of those conducting the research[4,5].

Currently, using various simulator software tools, it is possible to organize lectures, practical and laboratory classes, as well as independent learning of students.

For example, Crocodile - clips company's Crocodile Physics, Crocodile Technology, Crocodile Chemistry, Crocodile ICT programs, as well as Beginnings of Electronics, Interactive Physics, WorkingModel, Electronics Workbench, PhET Simulations, Pintar virtualLab Wave, MathCad, MatLab application packages and other software can be cited.

Crocodile Technology can be widely used by students and professors of higher education institutions as an additional pedagogical software tool in the disciplines of "Electrical Engineering", "Circuit Engineering", and "Theory of Electrical Circuits".

With the Crocodile Chemistry program, you can model chemical processes, model various reaction processes, and most importantly, do it safely.

Media education is a process of personal development aimed at forming a culture of interaction with the media using media resources, improving creativity, communication, and critical thinking skills through understanding, analyzing, interpreting, and evaluating media information, as well as teaching various forms of independent self-improvement using media technologies.

China's largest online platforms include 17zuoye and Cctalk. The 17zuoye platform aims to transform homework from offline to online, and translates from Chinese as "joint homework". The Cctalk platform was originally created as a bulletin board and later began offering online classes. The Cctalk platform operates as a database where you can find various educational programs related to learning foreign languages, preparing for international and national exams, professional skills, and many other areas.

The educational program of the Russian SkySmart School began with the Skyeng project, which taught free English to children and adolescents, and by 2019 it had expanded beyond a single subject to become an interactive school specializing in other subjects. Currently, the SkySmart School has a curriculum base in more than 15 subjects. This platform allows each child to choose the form of learning that suits them. They can participate in educational activities within the school curriculum, interactive educational quests, online peer camps, webinars, lectures, discussions, and study clubs.

In achieving the goals of improving the quality of education, improving the educational and methodological base in a way that meets the requirements of the time, introducing advanced information and communication technologies into the educational process, paying attention not only to the classroom form, but also to extracurricular forms of the educational process, creating and implementing new methods of organizing and managing it that meet the advanced requirements of the time and ensure the achievement of educational goals, as well as increasing the activity, independence, and motivation of students, as well as developing their professional competencies, remain urgent problems.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, today, media education, as a set of tools and methods for teaching students to produce their own educationally oriented media products, to perceive them independently, creatively and critically, is more relevant than ever.

A portal is a network telecommunications node that integrates various information resources to deliver information to the user through simple navigation and a comprehensive, user-friendly interface.

The goal of any portal is to provide the user with the information they need in a short time and without unnecessary transitions between different interfaces.

The information and educational resources provided will include tasks for independent activity and learning, tests to check acquired knowledge, tasks aimed at developing creative thinking, and exercises aimed at consolidating knowledge.

One of the important areas of reforming the education system is the systematic integration of the educational process with information and communication technologies. In this regard, the organization of the educational process and radical renewal of its content, the organization of the teacher's pedagogical activity and the student's independent learning process in the environment of information and communication technologies are manifested as strategic issues[6].

In conclusion, the above-mentioned websites that help students to work independently allow students and learners to study independently while staying at a distance. Websites that help students to study independently are especially convenient for students who have difficulty attending teaching locations.

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